

FACTORS OF ALKANOLAMINE CONTAMINATION WITH THERMOSTABLE SALTS IN NATURAL GAS PURIFICATION AND NEW DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR UTILIZATION

A.Mukhammadaliev

F.I.Kholmatova

Kh.N.Rakhimov

Kh.I.Kadirov

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18295628>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th January 2026

Accepted: 16th January 2026

Online: 17th January 2026

KEYWORDS

The reasons for the degradation of the diethanolamine solution used in natural gas purification are primarily related to factors affecting its physicochemical properties and absorption volume

ABSTRACT

The presence of CO₂ gas and chlorine ions in the gas supplied to the amine purification units of the Shurtan Oil and Gas Production Department and from the zeolite gas drying units leads to the formation of thermally resistant salts in the MDEA and DEA solutions used. As a result, mechanical impurities are formed in the amine solution due to iron ions, and surfactants appear in the composition of MDEA and DEA solutions. It should be especially noted that the accumulation of various salts and organic acids in the absorbent solution complicates the processes of purifying gases from toxic compounds. It leads to damage and failure of devices and equipment..

The presence of CO₂ gas and chlorine ions in the gas supplied to the amine purification units of the Shurtan Oil and Gas Production Department and from the zeolite gas drying units leads to the formation of thermally resistant salts in the MDEA and DEA solutions used. As a result, mechanical impurities are formed in the amine solution due to iron ions, and surfactants appear in the composition of MDEA and DEA solutions. It should be especially noted that the accumulation of various salts and organic acids in the absorbent solution complicates the processes of purifying gases from toxic compounds. It leads to damage and failure of devices and equipment.

The presence of thermally resistant components in the absorbent solution is substantiated, firstly, by their destruction with the absorption of oxygen in ethanolamine solutions, and secondly, by oxidation, heterocyclization, or polymerization reactions under the influence of oxygen absorbed by the solution during high-temperature regeneration of ethanolamines in a desorber. In this regard, numerous studies have been conducted worldwide to determine the causes of the formation of thermally resistant salts and the organic part of alkanolamines[1, 2]. The reasons for the degradation of the diethanolamine solution used in natural gas purification are primarily related to factors affecting its physicochemical properties and absorption volume. At the same time, studies of the composition of the regenerated absorbent show that the substances that need to be separated are (thermally resistant salts, organic carboxylic acids, bitins (N, N-bis (2-hydroxyethyl) glycine; diethylol glycine; diethanol glycine; dihydroxyethylglycine), di-, tri-,

tetra-compounds of amines). Based on the results of the study and analysis of the above, methods for purifying ethanolamines used in gas purification from harmful compounds and extending their service life were studied.

At the beginning of the research, a chromato-mass analysis of the 30% diethanolamine solution used at the "Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex" was conducted (Fig. 1), and it was shown that the composition of this absorbent is based on diethanolamine, with the addition of partial triethanolamine and a small amount of piperazine. The introduction of piperazine into the absorbent is associated with the absorption of carbon dioxide from natural gas [3-5].

Most of the non-regenerative products in the composition of the used alkanolamines are heterocyclic compounds, which are substantiated by the formation of DEA as a result of SO₂ interactions:

It has been established that the processes occur at different stages, and reaction schemes have been proposed. In the literature, it is shown that the formation of 2-oxazolidone in the working solution is the result of thermal transformations of carbamates:

It has also been proven that this substance is formed from N-hydroxyethylurea acid:

The formation of a reactive 2-oxazolidone with basic properties in the working solution leads to chemical transformations of many other heterocycles. For example, 1- (2-hydroxyethyl) -2-imidazolidone is a product of the reaction of 2-oxazolidone with another DEA molecule in a reaction medium:

N- (2-hydroxyethyl) -ethylenediamine molecules in the used amine are formed from the hydrolysis of 1- (2-hydroxyethyl) -2-imidazolidone:

Also, under the conditions of the amine system, many other products (compounds, carboxylic acids, carbonic acid anhydrides, and chlorates) are formed through chemical transformations:

Analyses show that at room temperature, carbon dioxide reacts with an aqueous solution to form unstable salts:

In an anhydrous medium, carbamic acids are formed under the influence of CO_2 :

The formation of chlorine derivatives is based on the action of thionyl chloride:

in an acidic medium, vinyl derivatives are formed:

With sodium and sodium chloride in solution, the following alcoholates are formed:

Diamines are formed by the reaction of ammonolization with the catalysis of metals and their salts contained in the used alkanolamines:

Under the action of concentrated H_2SO_4 , aminoethoxy sulfonic acids and their metallic complexes can be formed:

The presence of heterocycles of this type in the used DEA is the basis for testing them as inhibitors of mineral salt deposition. The DEA used at the beginning of the tests was subjected to adsorption purification [6] by known methods.

The used DEA was tested as a salt precipitation inhibitor. The results of the study show that at a DEA concentration of 6.0 mg/l, its effectiveness reaches 66.9%. Compositions were prepared by adding ODEF and IOMS-1 to the used DEA. The results of inhibiting the compositions are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Degree of protection of the used DEA, as well as its compositions with industrial inhibitors ODEF and IOMS-1

Composition of mineral salt accumulation inhibitor	Inhibitor concentration mg/l	Inhibitor effect, %			
		Water hardness, mg/l			
		4 - 5	8	11	-
		10		13	
I-MDEA	3,0	69,23	64,22	62,21	
	4,0	69,23	64,89	63,55	
	6,0	66,90	64,89	63,55	
IMDEA + OEDF	2,0 + 1,0	90,30	88,96	86,95	
	3,0 + 1,5	90,97	90,30	88,96	
	4,0 + 2,0	94,99	90,30	88,96	
IMDEA + IOMS-1	1,0 + 1,0	91,64	90,97	88,96	
	1,5 + 1,5	92,33	91,64	89,63	
	2,0 + 2,0	92,33	91,64	90,30	

As can be seen from the table data, the compositions obtained with the used DEA differ significantly compared to the use of pure ODEF and IOMS-1. At the same time, with the use of spent DEA, the cost of pure ODEF and IOMS-1 inhibitors can be reduced by 2.5-3.0 times.

References:

1. J. Price. Economic purification of amine solution // Oil and Gas Technologies. - 1996. - No. 1-2. - P. 58-59.
2. Keinard, M.L., Mason, A.B. Combating diethanolamine Losses [Text] // Oil, Gas and Petrochemistry Abroad. - 1980. - No 4. - P. 63-67.
3. A. Abdi, A. Meisen, Measurements of Vapor Pressure of Bis- (hydroxyethyl) piperazine and Tris (hydroxyethyl) ethylenediamine // J. Chem. Eng. Date. -1998. - P. 133-137.

4. Yu.I. Sustin, B.H. Sokolova, B.C. Prokopenko. Thermochemical degradation of ethanolamines. "Preparation, Processing and Use of Gas." - VNIIEGazprom. - No 2. - P. 3-8.
5. T.B. Turaev Kh.N. Rakhimov N.A. Igamkulova Sh.Sh. Mengliev. Determination of the Reasons for Degradation of a Diethanolamine Solution when Cleaning the Natural Gas and Methods for Cleaning Amine Solutions from Corrosive Active Substances.// International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology Vol. 7, Issue 2, February 2020
6. Rakhimov Khusniddin Nurboboevich. Restoration of the properties of ethanolamines used in the oil and gas industry and their reuse in the gas purification process. Dissertation of Doctor of Philosophy in Technical Sciences. Tashkent. 2022. 112 p

